

INTERACTIVE METHODS IN TEACHING ENGLISH TO PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Annotation. This article explores the use of interactive methods for preschool children in teaching English. The study is based on real personal teaching experience at a local kindergarten and concentrate on the usefulness of games, visual aids, physical activities and songs. The results showed that most children were eager to learn when using interactive techniques, comparing to traditional methods and learned faster. This also shows that using inductive and direct methods are highly effective for young learners. These findings suggest that interactive teaching methods can significantly enhance preschool English Education.

Keywords: interactive methods, preschool education, English language teaching, visual aids, songs, games, early childhood learning.

Introduction

In this modern day, learning foreign languages is very important. Knowing multiple languages opens many opportunities in education, career, and social interactions. Therefore, it's ideal to start in young age. Introducing the foreign languages to preschoolers is considered very important, because it is the stage when their minds are most adaptable and capable of learning a lot of new information. However, it's not easy for preschool children to teach English, because they are too young to sit in one place for a long time and they have short attention spans. Therefore, the traditional approach may not be effective. Instead, interactive methods - games, visual aids, songs and movement activities have proven to be successful in creating both enjoyable and meaningful learning experience, and support the development of language naturally. This article aims to show how to use interactive methods effectively in English lessons with preschool children, based on practical teaching experiences.

Methods

This study is based on my own teaching experience at Qaldirgoch Kindergarten, where I taught English to two age-based groups: children aged 5–6 and 6–7, with over thirty students in each group. Lessons were held twice a week. I began each class with a warm-up activity using physical commands like “stand up,” “jump,” and “fly” to capture the children’s attention and prepare them for learning.

I also incorporated movement-based video games, where children responded to cues like “swim” or “freeze.” These activities not only made the lessons fun but also helped improve their pronunciation.

To develop vocabulary, I used the Direct Method, introducing new words through real-life objects—for instance, by pointing to the wall, curtain, or light to teach colors. Games such as “Which one is green?” and the use of flashcards helped reinforce the vocabulary in a visual and interactive way.

Each lesson ended with action songs like “Peel Banana” and “This is Big, Big, Big,” accompanied by gestures. I also used a voice-level repetition technique where students repeated words at different volumes depending on the position of the flashcard. The sessions always ended on a cheerful note, with the children happily saying, “Goodbye, teacher!”

Results

After using interactive methods, such as songs, flashcards and games, children showed the result of improvement in their vocabulary and pronunciation. Despite being very young, most children could remember colors and fruits’ names even after two lessons. During games, they were able to point to the correct object and say the word with confidence.

Kids were really motivated and engaged. They laughed, smiled during the lesson and asked to repeat the action video games. Even some shy children tried to go out from their comfort zone and began to participate in the lesson. Movement games helped them concentrate and action songs created a positive environment.

At the end, all children were happy and responded especially well to these methods. Middle group enjoyed the songs and voice-level activities the most, compared to older group who learned faster and could say longer sentences.

Discussion

The results of this study suggest that interactive methods are very useful in teaching English to preschool children. The children responded positively showed enthusiasm to games, songs, flashcards, and real-life examples, which kept them engaged and motivated. These findings reflect the importance of adapting teaching methods to the developmental needs of young learners, who have short attention spans and learn best through movement and sensory input. Similar studies have also highlighted the effectiveness usefulness of interactive and gamified teaching methods in enhancing language learning for preschoolers (Benitez Sandoval, 2022).

The methods used in this study align with several established teaching approaches. For example, the inductive method was used when new vocabulary was introduced through examples before giving any explanation or rule. This approach allowed children to learn naturally, without pressure. The direct method was also present, as English was taught using real objects and actions rather than translation into the native language. This helped the learners understand meaning visually and contextually. These findings are in line with research by Islam et al. (2014), who found that interactive methods, including visual aids and multimedia materials, help increase preschoolers’ language learning efficiency.

Although the interactive methods were effective, there were some challenges. Working with large groups of over 30 children made it difficult to give individual attention. Some children, especially the youngest, needed more time to adapt to classroom routines or follow instructions. Despite these limitations, the majority of the learners benefited greatly from the interactive strategies, and their energy proved the value of the methods used. Cerezo et al (2024) found similar challenges in their study, noting that while large class sizes posed difficulties, interactive methods like mobile-based applications for pronunciation still showed positive results for language acquisition.

These findings suggest that teachers working with young learners should incorporate interactive elements- especially songs, movement, and visual support into their lessons. Such methods both support language learning and create a joyful and engaging classroom environment.

Conclusion

This study has shown interactive teaching methods for preschool children, such as songs, games, visual aids and movement activities which are highly effective for teaching English. These methods helped children increase their vocabulary ranges and support better pronunciation. In spite of some challenges, like large class sizes, the benefits were clear and consistent. It is suggested that preschool teachers should use interactive strategies to create a more effective teaching environment.

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